

In vitro and in vivo pharmacodynamic activity of the new compound XC221GI in models of the viral inflammation of the respiratory tract

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Assessment criteria for pathology in cotton rats with RSV infection

For each sample, four slides were presented with sections of cotton rat lungs stained with H&E, Duffy, PAS, and toluidine blue. Samples were randomized for blind evaluation. All slides contained cross-oblique sections of the three right lung lobes (cephalic, middle, and inferior). For most specimens, head and lower lobe sections consisted of thoracic and proximal profiles of the main axial airways.

The slides were evaluated for the presence of peribronchiolitis, interstitial inflammatory cell infiltrates (pneumonia), and alveolitis. In each of these inflammatory components, the extent of mononuclear leukocyte infiltration was assessed along with minor polymorphonuclear leukocyte (PML) infiltration. PML was further differentiated and scored as neutrophilic and/or eosinophilic by Duffy histochemical staining. Slides stained with toluidine blue were used to assess the number, distribution, and morphology of mast cells. Mucosal / goblet cell proliferation and expansion was assessed based on PAS-stained regions. In addition, mucosal cell hyperplasia/hypertrophy and bronchiolar epithelial hyperplasia were evaluated.

Peribronchiolitis

Almost all specimens had some degree of infiltration of the peribronchiolar stroma with mononuclear and polymorphonuclear leukocytes (peribronchiolitis). The gradation of peribronchiolitis included inflammation also affecting the connective tissue surrounding large blood vessels, which are closely related to the conducting airways. In many specimens, primary mononuclear inflammation was concentrated around the largest airways, but in more affected specimens, inflammation extended to the entire length of the conducting airways, including the smaller and terminal bronchioles. The degree of penetration of PML, including neutrophils and eosinophils, into the peribronchiolar stroma was also

assessed. There were many PML in moderate peribronchiolar infiltrates, especially in the submucosal stroma. PML around poorly affected airways sometimes aggregated into small loose cell clusters with more marked transmigration of neutrophils and eosinophils into the mucosal epithelium.

Severity scores for peribronchiolar inflammatory leukocyte infiltrates/bronchiolitis (“inflammation of the airways”) in RSV-infected cotton rats were graded according to the following gradation.

Minimal airway inflammation (grade 1). Small numbers of mononuclear leukocytes (lymphocytes, mostly with occasional macrophages and occasional plasma cells) scattered widely or loosely arranged in small aggregates, mostly in the stromal interstitium, deep in the airway smooth muscle layer with some leukocytes between the muscle bundles and fewer cells in the submucosal stroma in the depth of the mucosal epithelium. PML infiltrates are mixed with mononuclear cells and are characterized by widely disseminated PML in the stroma deep in the smooth muscle layer of the peribronchiolar interstitium.

Mild inflammation of the airways (grade 2). More numerous mononuclear leukocytes and denser cells in the deeper interstitium often disrupt or displace smooth muscle bundles superficially. Multifocal and confluent patches of mononuclear inflammatory cells in the submucosal stroma, directly deep into the mucosal epithelium, and slight stretching/expansion of the stromal interstitium and submucosa. Mild inflammation mixed with mononuclear cells has more numerous PML, especially prominent in the submucosal stroma and sometimes aggregated into small clusters of cells. More noticeable is the transmigration of PML into the mucosal epithelium (granulocytic bronchiolitis).

Moderate airway inflammation (grade 3). Usually more widespread and rather densely aggregated leukocytes at all stromal levels and with expansion of all compartments (especially in the submucosa). Mononuclear cells are packed up to 30 cell layers thick deep in some

areas. Scattered infiltration of the epithelium by a few mononuclear cells often accompanies peribronchiolar infiltrates (i.e., lymphocytic bronchiolitis). Sometimes mononuclear leukocytes spread into the adjacent interstitium of the alveolar septa. PML is usually no more numerous than in mild inflammation.

Inflammation is concentrated around the largest airways, but in more severely affected specimens, inflammation extends around nearly all conducting airways, including smaller bronchioles and terminal bronchioles. PML is more localized than lymphocytes in the free connective tissue surrounding the thoracic airways and in the interstitium around first-generation bronchioles and does not extend into the perivascular tissue of the smallest airways even when the mononuclear leukocyte intrusion is more extensive.

Additionally, in the peribronchiolar stroma, the number and morphology of mast cells were assessed in areas stained with toluidine blue. The mast cells were not numerous and appeared to be compact and well granulated. Cell degranulation was not evident. Mast cells were distributed in the connective tissue around the large airways and blood vessels; rarely, one cell was noted in the terminal bronchiolar submucosa. The number of cells was estimated according to the following gradation: less than 150 cells per sample – 1, from 150 to 250 cells – 2, more than 250 cells – 3.

Alveolitis and interstitial pneumonia

Parenchymal inflammation in this study consisted of inflammatory cell infiltrates of the alveolar septum (interstitial infiltrates/pneumonia) as well as inflammatory cell exudates in the alveolar air spaces (alveolitis).

As a rule, alveolitis and foci of interstitial pneumonia were located near the terminal bronchioles, and the parenchyma near the chyle often turned out to be more severe. Most specimens contained 20 to 30 terminal bronchioles, and no more than $\frac{1}{4}$ - $\frac{1}{3}$ of these were affected by surrounding alveolitis and interstitial infiltrates/pneumonia.

Minimal alveolitis (grade 1) had scattered alveolar air spaces in a high magnification area that had few neutrophils and up to 5 alveolar macrophages.

In moderate alveolitis (grade 2), adjacent alveoli in several high-magnification scattered areas contained a

few neutrophils (up to 5 or more per alveolus) and up to 10–20 alveolar macrophages per field.

In the presence of parenchymal interstitial infiltrates, type II epithelial hyperplasia was often observed. The severity of hyperplasia and hypertrophy was combined with distribution scores.

With minimal severity (grade 1), a small number or small groups of mucous cells were located in single layers, in foci scattered quite widely in the epithelium of the mucous membrane of large and medium bronchioles.

With moderate hyperplasia (grade 2) and hypertrophy, larger groups of mucous cells were observed, sometimes in layers of up to 2 or 3 cells thick.

In moderate hypertrophy / hyperplasia (grade 3) of mucosal cells, extensive areas of mucosal epithelium occupied by cells were observed, each containing a fairly large number of apical mucus granules and layers of 3 or 4 cells thick, especially at the branching points of the bronchioles.

Mucosal hyperplasia/hypertrophy was assessed as follows: focal (grade 1), local extensive (grade 2), multifocal (grade 3), and multifocal confluent (grade 4) where large areas of the epithelium were occupied by these cells.

Additionally, the epithelium of the respiratory mucosa was assessed for cell proliferation (hyperplasia) and cell death (apoptosis/necrosis). In some specimens, slight to moderate proliferation of simple cuboidal or columnar epithelium was noted in small airways. The cells were randomly arranged in stratified or small papilla-like structures protruding into the lumen of the air passages. This pathology was graded from complete absence (grade 0) to moderate (grade 2).

To analyze differences between groups, scores were summarized for individual areas. For example, in peribronchiolitis, severity scores for mononuclear infiltrates, neutrophil infiltrates, eosinophil infiltrates, and mast cell infiltrates were added to give a total score.

Similar overall scores were made for alveolitis and interstitial infiltrates. For mucosal hyperplasia / hypertrophy, severity scores were multiplied by distribution scores to obtain a pathology score for subsequent group analysis. Bronchiolar epithelial hyperplasia scores were added to apoptosis data to provide an overall assessment of bronchiolar epithelial change. These scores were added together to obtain a total histopathology score.